

Scaling-up microwave-assisted synthesis of highly defective Pd@UiO-66-NH₂ catalysts for selective olefin hydrogenation under ambient conditions

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Abstract

The need to develop green and cost-effective industrial catalytic processes has led to a growing interest in preparing more robust, efficient, and selective heterogeneous catalysts at a large scale. In this regard, microwave-assisted synthesis is a fast method for fabricating heterogeneous catalysts (including metal oxides, zeolites, metal-organic frameworks and supported metal nanoparticles) with enhanced catalytic properties, enabling synthesis scaling-up. Herein, the synthesis of nanosized UiO-66-NH₂ was optimized via microwave-assisted hydrothermal method to obtain defective matrices essential for the stabilization of metal nanoparticles, promoting catalytically active sites for hydrogenation reactions (760 Kg·m⁻³·day⁻¹ space-time yield, STY). Then, this protocol was scaled-up in a multimodal microwave reactor, reaching 86% yield (*ca.* 1 g, 1450 Kg·m⁻³·day⁻¹ STY) in only 30 min. Afterwards, Pd nanoparticles were formed *in situ* decorating the nanoMOF by an effective and fast microwave-assisted hydrothermal method, resulting in the formation of Pd@UiO-66-NH₂ composites. Both the localization and oxidation state of Pd nanoparticles (NPs) in the MOF were achieved using high-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADF-STEM) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), respectively. The optimal composite, loaded with 1.7 wt% Pd, exhibited an extraordinary catalytic activity (>95% yield, 100% selectivity) under mild conditions (1 bar H₂, 25 °C, 1 h reaction time), not only in the selective hydrogenation of a variety of single alkenes (1-hexene, 1-octene, 1-tridecene, cyclohexene and tetraphenyl ethylene) but also in the conversion of a complex mixture of alkenes (*i.e.*, 1-hexene, 1-tridecene, and anethole). The results

showed a powerful interaction and synergy between the active phase (Pd NPs) and the catalytic porous scaffold (UiO-66-NH₂), essential for the selectivity and recyclability.

Keywords: microwave-assisted synthesis, defect engineering, UiO-66-NH₂, gram-scale, selective hydrogenation, palladium

1. Introduction

At the moment, 90% of the chemicals requires the presence of a catalyst during their industrial production,¹ being of extreme importance in the case of pharmaceuticals or refined petrochemicals. Efforts are currently focused on the design of more efficient and economically profitable methodologies.² However, the integration of such catalyst in industrial processes is not exempt of relevant limitations, *e.g.* catalysts passivation and/or poisoning, aspects with a dramatic impact over their lifetime and recyclability, particularly when moving from batch to continuous operation.

Catalytic hydrogenation is one of the most widespread reactions within the industry because of the extensive range of chemical products that can be obtained, including fine chemicals, fuels or fibers, among others.³ In particular, the reduction of olefins has been broadly studied upon adding metal-based homogeneous catalysts, including Ni,⁴ Pd,⁵ and Pt,⁶ in the presence of hydrogen donors. However, several aspects related to their recyclability, cost and/or toxicity have hampered their use in industrial processes. Nowadays, large-scale hydrogenation is typically performed in the presence of palladium-based composites such as Pd/C and Pd/Al₂O₃⁷ since Pd nanoparticles (Pd NPs) exhibit an exceptional catalytic activity and high chemical reactivity.⁸ In such materials, the low stability and limited recyclability of isolated Pd NPs,⁹ ascribed to their aggregation, have been partially circumvented by immobilizing them within convenient porous supports.¹⁰ In this sense, different Pd-based composites have been studied in the last years in order to improve the overall catalytic performance, minimizing the metal content, preventing metal leaching and finding the optimal synergy between the catalyst itself and the support. The ultimate challenge has revealed to be the passivation of Pd surface and the progressive obstruction of diffusion channels in porous materials hampering the accessibility of chemicals towards metal binding sites. Besides, the principles of the green chemistry should be observed, *i.e.* novel synthetic procedures must be scalable at industrial level. Thus, there is an urgent need for: i) the preparation of convenient heterogenous catalysts in the form of composites to reduce the catalyst loading and improve recyclability; and ii) a large-scale synthetic protocol minimizing the fabrication cost by decreasing reaction times and making a better use of the starting materials.

In this context, metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), comprised of organic linkers and metal ions, have emerged as potential catalytic supports thanks to their inherent porosity and the presence of coordinatively unsaturated sites (CUS), allowing for a fast diffusion of chemicals and their interaction with active sites, thus decreasing the energy barrier of a broad variety of reactions.¹¹ These hybrid polymers have been used in different manners for catalysis: a) as-synthesized, because of the presence of CUS within the structure, typically acting as Lewis/Brønsted acidic sites;¹² b) introducing new open

metal sites and transition metal complexes by pre- or post-synthetic modification of organic linkers or MOFs (*i.e.* organic and inorganic parts), respectively;^{13c}) by loading catalytically active metal cations inside the porous cages and, if necessary, followed by their reduction to metal colloids that remain confined within the pores.¹⁴ Several authors have reported a synergetic catalytic performance of MOF-based composites when metal nanoparticles are included, due to any of the following effects: a) the activity of the structural metal itself is enhanced, b) the accessibility of chemicals to the new metal sites is improved, or c) a singular spatial rearrangement of the chemicals anchored within the pores is displayed that cannot be observed otherwise. Moreover, nucleation and growth of such metal nanoparticles are extraordinarily controlled because of the confinement effect attributed to the pores which, in addition, provide further stability to the colloid.¹⁵

The role of defects in MOFs has been demonstrated to be of extreme relevance for boosting the catalytic performance.¹⁶ In particular, hydrogenation reactions have shown remarkable improvements when using defective matrices.¹⁷ Although proposed in the late 2000s, defect engineering irrupted in MOF technology by the mid-2010s, when hundreds of unexplored structures appeared allowing for significant structural modifications without remarkable collapse.¹⁸ Since then, several strategies to generate defects have been proposed including modifications in the synthesis (mechanochemical, sonochemical), pre- and post-synthetic modifications, chemical etching, or the use of surfactants, among others.^{18, 19,20}

From the extensive plethora of available MOFs, the microporous zirconium-terephthalate UiO-66 (*Universitetet i Oslo*) has called a great attention from the catalytic community^{21,22} due to its facile synthesis, high stability and relevant physicochemical properties, whose origin relies on the Zr-O-based node despite the high coordination of the cluster.²³ Interestingly, catalysis can be promoted not only through Brønsted acid sites in the nodes,²⁴ but also upon *in situ* reduction of cations yielding metal colloids within the pores. Inducing defects in the UiO-66 matrix has been also extensively studied, particularly by using different acidic modulators and microwave radiation.^{25,26,27} Typically, monodentate carboxylates occupy linker positions during the MOF synthesis, thus resulting in missing linker positions when washing and activating the material. UiO-66 shows a wide flexibility in terms of defect generation, even allowing up to 67% ligand replacement without collapsing.²⁸ These defects considerably attract Pd(II) cations that can easily diffuse throughout the network within a few seconds by a simple wet impregnation.²⁹ On the other hand, the use of 2-aminoterephthalic acid as the organic ligand (*i.e.* UiO-66-NH₂) enhances, even more, the stability of Pd species with the aid of -NH₂ moieties.³⁰ Besides, the use of microwave radiation brings into scene the additional benefit of improving phase purity and yields by decreasing reaction time and particle size, aside from introducing a larger amount of defects,^{31,32} all of them critical aspects in catalysis.

However, there are only a few examples in the literature reporting on the use of metal NPs@UiO-66-NH₂ for the hydrogenation of alkenes and aromatic hydrocarbons.³³ In 2014, Huan *et al.*³⁴ solvothermally prepared the Pt@UiO-66-NH₂ composite in 24 h, which showed a limited catalytic activity in the hydrogenation of light olefins at 35 °C and 1 bar H₂ (66% conversion of cyclooctene after 24 h). Ning *et al.*³⁵ reported the solvothermal synthesis of Pd@UiO-66 and its further Pd impregnation, obtaining the composite after 48 h that was studied for phenol hydrogenation (100% conversion, at 20 bar H₂ and 60 °C for 16 h) lacking specific mention to the catalyst stability. Similar procedure was reported by Li *et al.*³⁶ for the preparation of Pd@UiO-66-NH₂ which also displayed a high styrene conversion (91%) but at 50 °C and for 15 h. More recently, Liu *et al.*³⁷ prepared a Pt/UiO-66-NH₂ composite *via* solvothermal synthesis in the presence of polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP)-stabilized Pt NPs, achieving a low activity in the hydrogenation of cyclooctene and *trans*-stilbene (*ca.* 50% conversion) at 35 °C and 1 atm H₂ after 24 h. Despite these interesting results, reported methods are not enough time- and cost-efficient.

In the present work, we have prepared a Pd@UiO66-NH₂ composite using a more effective microwave-assisted hydrothermal route (1.5 h vs. 24 to 48 h in reported conventional solvothermal methodologies), even achieving full conversion with less severe reaction conditions (1 bar H₂, room temperature, 1 h reaction time). Moreover, we have: i) optimized the synthesis protocol of UiO-66-NH₂ using a monomodal microwave instrument (91±5% yield in only 20 min reaction time) to find the optimal candidate for catalytic purposes in terms of textural properties, particle size, stability and defects; ii) scaled-up this procedure in a multimodal microwave reactor (gram-scale, 84±3% yield) and, after a wet impregnation with Pd(II) and a fast microwave-assisted reduction step (150 °C for 10 min) the Pd@UiO-66-NH₂ composite was obtained and characterized (Pd NP size 3-4 nm); iii) used successfully the MOF composite as catalyst for the selective hydrogenation of olefins (including hydrogenation of a mixture of three alkenes), under mild conditions (1 atm H₂, 25 °C, 1 h); and iv) studied the interaction and the synergetic effect between the Pd NPs and the MOF scaffold by using high-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADF-STEM) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS).

2. Experimental

2.1. Synthesis

Materials

All chemicals were purchased from commercial companies and used without purification: zirconium (IV) oxychloride octahydrate ($\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Sigma Aldrich, 99.5%), zirconium chloride (ZrCl_4 , Sigma Aldrich, 99.5%) and zirconium propoxide ($\text{Zr}(\text{OPr})_4$, Sigma Aldrich 70 wt% in 1-propanol), palladium (II) chloride (PdCl_2 , Merck, 99%), sodium borohydride (NaBH_4 , Sigma Aldrich, 98%), 2-aminoterephthalic acid (2ATA, Acros Organics, 99%), *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF, Chemlab, 99%), trifluoroacetic acid (TFA, ACROS Organics, 99%), acetic acid glacial (Supelco), formic acid (Thermo Scientific, 98%), absolute ethanol (Molecular Biology Grade, Fisher), acetone (HPLC Grade, Chem-lab), and poly(vinylpyrrolidone) (PVP, MW=30000, AR).

For comparative purposes, PVP-stabilized Pd nanoparticles (PVP@Pd NPs) were prepared according to a microwave-assisted method reported elsewhere³⁸ and $\text{Pd}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ was purchased from Sigma Aldrich.

Synthesis of UiO-66-NH₂

Fabrication of nanometric UiO-66-NH₂ crystals was performed in a monomodal microwave instrument (Anton Paar Monowave 300) by adapting a protocol described in the literature,³⁹ with some minor modifications. Optimization tests can be found in Table S1. Selection of the optimal MOF was performed after the analysis of the candidates by powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and nitrogen sorption. The optimal synthetic protocol for the monomodal instrument is described as follows: $\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (296 mg; 0.92 mmol) and 2ATA (167 mg; 0.92 mmol) were dissolved in 10 mL DMF inside a 30-mL glass microwave vial. TFA (0.71 mL; 9.23 mmol) was added to the mixture and then, the vial was placed in the microwave instrument. Synthesis consisted of 3 steps: i) a ramp to reach 175 °C, from room temperature, in 5 min: ii) keeping 175 °C for 20 min (max. pressure: 14.0 bar, 15-20 W to maintain the temperature in the form of pulsed irradiation); iii) cooling to 60 °C with an air flow. The pale-yellow suspension was centrifuged (12000 rpm, 15 min), and the gel-like solid washed by resuspension using fresh DMF (30 mL, ×3) and absolute ethanol (30 mL, ×3), under similar centrifugation conditions. Solid was transferred to a 25-mL glass vial and dried for 12 h at 100 °C to obtain a yellowish material with the consistency of a foam (316.7 mg; 91±5% yield ($n = 5$)) on metal basis considering the structural formula $\text{Zr}_6\text{O}_4(\text{OH})_4(2\text{ATA})_5(\text{TFA})_2(\text{DMF})_4$ with a MW = 2091.4 g·mol⁻¹, in agreement to the TGA results). Space-Time Yield (STY) was estimated to be 760 Kg·m⁻³·day⁻¹.

The material was scaled-up ($\times 3.3$) afterwards in a multimodal microwave instrument (One Touch Technology Mars6 240/50). Briefly, $\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (980 mg; 3.04 mmol) and 2-ATA (540 mg; 2.98 mmol) were dissolved in 33 mL DMF inside a 45-mL microwave Teflon-lined reactor. TFA (2.34 mL; 30.58 mmol) was then added to the mixture and the reaction proceeded in the same manner as described above. A similar procedure was followed in order to wash and activate the material. Yield (metal basis) was $84 \pm 3\%$ ($n = 5$) (908.6 mg), lower than that obtained with the monomodal reactor but with higher STY ($1450 \text{ Kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$).

Synthesis of Pd@UiO-66-NH₂

The preparation of Pd@UiO-66-NH₂ was performed by wet impregnation of the metal precursor followed by a chemical reduction in one pot using the previous multimodal microwave instrument. UiO-66-NH₂ (83.00 mg, 0.04 mmol), PdCl₂ (2 or 5 wt% Pd) and Mili-Q water (10 mL) were added to a Teflon-lined reactor. The mixture was kept under magnetic stirring for 30 minutes and then, 1 mL of a solution consisting of NaBH₄ (3 mg·mL⁻¹ in MeOH) was added dropwise under vigorous stirring for 20 min. Finally, the resulting suspension was heated using a 5 min ramp from 25 to 150 °C and maintained for 10 min. After cooling, the composite was recovered as a grayish solid by filtration (nylon, 0.22 μm) and washed several times with deionized water. The resulting materials were denoted as Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ and Pd(4.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ containing 1.7 and 4.7 wt% of Pd, respectively.

2.2. Hydrogenation reactions

The activity and selectivity of the as-prepared composites were studied in hydrogenation reactions of different alkenes (including 1-hexene, 1-octene, 1-tridecene, cyclohexene and tetraphenyl ethylene), using a batch pressurized stainless steel polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE)-lined reactor (100 mL, miniclave from Buchiglas), at 1 bar (gas, H₂, 99.9998 %), and 25 °C. 10 mg of catalyst was dispersed in alkene solution (5 mmol in 25 mL of acetyl acetate). The reactor was purged three times prior to the reaction by increasing the H₂ pressure up to 1 bar and opening the output valve. Then, the reactor was pressurized once again with 1 bar of H₂ and the reaction was considered to begin when the magnetic stirring started. After 1 h, the stirring was stopped and the output valve was opened, ending the reaction. The composite was recovered by filtration and dried at 80 °C in a furnace for 3 h. The resulting solution was analyzed by gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS) (Agilent 8860 GC-5977B GC/MSD equipped with a HP5-MS UI column 30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 mm) and the concentration of all products and byproducts obtained was calculated with an external calibration, using cyclohexanol as internal standard.

2.3. Characterization

Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) patterns were acquired in a PANalytical[®] Empyrean powder diffractometer (PANalytical, Lelyweg, The Netherlands) with a Cu K α = 1.5406 Å in reflection mode with a 2 Θ scan between 3°-50° (MOFs) and 3°-90° (composite) with a step of 0.013° and a scanning speed of 0.1 °·s⁻¹. Fourier-transform infrared spectra (FTIR) were collected in a Nicolet 6700 (Thermo Scientific, USA) in an attenuated total reflectance (ATR) mode using a diamond accessory. Spectra were obtained with 32 scans and a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹, within 4000-400 cm⁻¹. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was carried out in an SDT Q-600 thermobalance (TA Instruments, New Castle, De, USA) with a heating profile from room temperature to 800 °C, under oxidative conditions (air; 100 mL·min⁻¹), and a heating rate of 5 °C·min⁻¹. Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) was performed in a Perkin Elmer Optima 7300 DV (samples were previously digested using a piranha solution). Nitrogen sorption isotherms were acquired in a Micromeritics Tristar II PLUS at 77 K after activating the samples (*ca.* 50-100 mg) at 150 °C for 16 h under primary vacuum. The specific surface area was calculated according to the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) equation in the relative pressures range $P/P_0 = 0.01-0.30$. Pore size distribution was estimated with the Horvath-Kawazoe (HK) method (using spherical model) and pore volume and pore area were estimated with the t-plot method in the relative pressures range $P/P_0 = 0.01-0.80$. Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) images were obtained in a JEOL (JSM 7900F) scanning microscope at an accelerating voltage of 10 kV. Samples for transmission electron microscopy (TEM) were prepared by casting a drop of solution onto a Cu TEM grid coated with amorphous carbon. Routine TEM images were acquired using a JEOL microscope (JEM 1400 FLASH) with a 200 kV acceleration voltage with a secondary detector to perform energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) measurements for elemental analysis. To acquire high angle annular dark field scanning TEM (HAADF-STEM) images, an aberration corrected Thermo Fisher Scientific Titan Cubed electron microscope, operated at 300 kV, was used. The camera length was set at 230 mm, and the probe convergence semi-angle was 15 mrad, yielding inner and outer HAADF detector collection semi-angles of 26 and 155 mrad, respectively.

3. Results and discussion

Defects in MOFs are essential for catalysis and can be introduced throughout/within the matrices in different manners, including: i) nano-sizing (higher exposure of metal active sites); ii) generation of defective positions around CUS by using modulators; iii) formation of novel CUS by ligand modification or cation grafting, which can be additionally reduced to originate colloidal aggregates.^{16,17,40,41} In this sense, UiO-66-NH₂ was chosen because it:⁴² a) shows an extraordinary thermal and chemical robustness under harsh conditions (reported thermal decomposition temperature values from 425 to 500 °C); b) allows an extensive inclusion of defects and chemical/physical modifications; and c) carries amino moieties capable to interact with other metal species, acting as secondary metal active sites. Several authors have demonstrated the superior catalytic performance of UiO-66 when downsizing the particle size below 100 nm, acquiring a gel-like consistency for particles < 30 nm.⁴³ This aspect is of extreme relevance since such gels can be easily shaped through different methodologies, being promising candidates as catalysts because of the high tolerance of this framework when generating defects (up to 67% ligands can be removed) without suffering structural damage, which also circumvents mass transfer limitations. Note that, despite UiO-66-NH₂ is a robust material in terms of fabrication and stability in a broad range of harsh conditions, the compactness of the framework and the high coordination of the Zr-cluster may prevent the accessibility and coordination of reagents to catalytically active sites.^{44,45} Both “missing linker” and “missing metal cluster” defects (with respect to the ideal UiO-66 structure) exist as a result of terephthalate ligands being replaced by other coordinative molecules.⁴⁶ Indeed, the number of defects found in UiO-66 crystals and its analogues depends on the synthetic conditions, where modulators play a leading role.^{18,39,47}

3.1. Microwave-assisted synthesis of UiO-66-NH₂

Considering the abovementioned premises, we evaluated 3 reaction parameters in the synthesis of UiO-66-NH₂: nature and amount of modulator, and reaction time. The optimal candidate should be the one providing a compromise between crystallinity (homogeneity of physicochemical properties distributed alongside the whole extent of the material), particle size (easy manipulation and separation; high CUS exposure), stability and surface area (high adsorption capacity for metal cations while facilitating reagents' diffusion) and production of the largest amount of MOF in the shortest reaction time. Thus, 12 different syntheses were performed in a monomodal microwave instrument (Table S1), screening the resulting UiO-66-NH₂ materials by means of their crystal size (DLS and PXRD, Figure S1), decomposition temperature and number of defects (TGA, Figure S2), BET surface area (Figure

S3) and IR spectroscopy (Figure S4) as a function of both the modulator (amount of TFA; 0, 0.32, 0.62, 0.86 ad 1.19 M) and reaction time (5 or 20 min) (Table S1).

Regarding the acidity of the modulator, we selected TFA for the synthesis. Although previously discarded by other authors because of the crystal aggregation,⁴⁷ TFA was here the acid providing the largest amount of network defects and BET surface area under the fixed reaction conditions tested (175 °C, 1:1 metal:ligand *mol/mol* in 10 mL DMF), maintaining the structural stability in agreement with previous observations.^{48,49} Stronger modulators, *i.e.* those acids showing low pK_a values, remain attached to the metal cluster during the polymer synthesis, providing additional “missing linker” positions after material activation. Weaker acids such as acetic acid ($pK_a = 4.76$; Table S1, entry 5) or formic acid ($pK_a = 3.77$), with a similar pK_a to the linker (3.51, 4.82), have resulted in larger but less defective crystals, because of the capacity of the ligand to replace them.⁴⁴ Other Zr(IV) precursors were also tested with similar (in the case of Zr(OPr)₄) or poorer results (when using ZrCl₄) (Table S1, entries 4, 11 and 12). However, in the case of the alkoxide, the matrix acquired a higher compactness and periodicity after 20 min, as revealed from the defect calculation (see Table S1), pointing to a linker excess. Something similar occurred when using the chloride precursor, showing a lower number of linker defects than that obtained with TFA and, in this case, significantly decreasing the BET surface area (from 937 to 182 m²·g⁻¹), suggesting that the linkers remain attached to the framework either onto MOF surface or within the porosity, but not occupying their natural crystallographic position.

To better observe the influence of the different parameters, contour density maps of crystal size, decomposition temperature, number of defects and BET surface area were represented as a function of both the modulator and the reaction time (Figure 1). Horizontal extended color regions denote that reaction time had little influence over the studied parameters, except if using a low concentration of TFA. In absence of modulators, crystalline domain size (calculated from (111) diffraction peak by using Scherrer equation)⁴⁷ decreased, probably because of the chemical etching of nuclei being indiscriminately attacked by basic species from DMF decomposition (dimethylamine) under microwave radiation.^{50,51} As a consequence, those crystals showed the lowest thermal stability, number of defects and BET surface area. Note here that the defects evaluated in this work are related to the internal structure of the UiO-66-NH₂ network in terms of missing linkers, thus being estimated from TGA residues.^{27, 28,52} The addition of acidic modulators partially mitigated this phenomenon, resulting in a progressive color plateau as a function of time (x-axis) after increasing modulator concentration (y-axis). In fact, modulators accomplished here 2 distinctive roles: as defect inducers and base scavengers, preventing the attack from basic species. Color changes were more evident along the y-axis, *i.e.* TFA concentration modified the final features of such MOFs with a higher impact than time,

particularly when the amount of modulator used in their synthesis was enough (ratio > 5.7:1 modulator:linker, *mol/mol*).

Figure 1. Density contour plots of: a) crystal size (estimated by using Scherrer equation from PXRD); b) decomposition temperature (first derivative of TGA curves); c) number of defects (TGA, compared to theoretical weights at different temperatures; in terms of missing linker units); d) BET surface area (using nitrogen sorption isotherms); as a function of modulator concentration and reaction time. Red indicates the highest values, while blue means the opposite.

The highest defect concentration was found in the MOF showing both the best crystallinity (narrower diffraction peaks) and a large crystalline domain size. Decomposition temperatures suggested that the larger number of defects, the higher resistance towards heating. Other authors have reported the opposite behavior in UiO-66-NH₂ networks, as one should have expected.²⁷ We hypothesized that defects created in our work were not enough in number to observe such decrease in thermal stability, probably ascribed to the presence of extensive defects in the cited report (up to 1830 m²·g⁻¹ BET surface area) instead quasi-punctual defects as in here (970 m²·g⁻¹), vs the crystallographic value of 876 m²·g⁻¹.⁵³ Recently, some authors have demonstrated that symmetrically distributed (spatially correlated) defects in UiO-66 considerably improved the thermal properties compared to randomly distributed missing linkers,⁵⁴ which is the most common situation. Defect arrangement induced by microwave radiation could be behind this phenomenon, as a consequence of dipolar moment alignment of modulator molecules in predefined directions when attaching the metal clusters

generating this anisotropy, as previously described for other semiconductor materials.⁵⁵ Demonstration, besides complicated through advanced techniques (nanodomain crystalline resolution), is far from the scope of this work. This manner of generating defects favored the stability of the network and the cation impregnation in further steps and revealed to be crucial for potential utilization at the industrial level.⁵⁶

ATR-FTIR spectra (Figure S4) showed the vibration corresponding to Zr-O ($648\text{-}655\text{ cm}^{-1}$) probing the coordination between the ligand and the metal cluster after 5 and 20 min. COO vibrations, originally located at 1220 and 1670 cm^{-1} , suffered a significant shift upon linker coordination to $1250\text{-}1253$ and $1651\text{-}1655\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively, as well as a decrease in their intensity. Other minor differences between MOFs synthesized at different reaction times was the band at 780 cm^{-1} assigned to CCOO, that disappeared in the spectra after 20 min but still remarkable after 5 min, demonstrating the high number of degrees of freedom still available in the structure and supporting the previous evidences which highlight the gel behavior of such polymers.⁵⁷

From a practical point of view, those MOFs obtained after 5 min were directly discarded because the complexity in their handling (washing, centrifuging, etc.). Besides, we required the optimal compromise between defect concentration and other related physicochemical properties. The fact of showing up to 30% missing linkers, despite favoring mass transfer, would have negatively impacted the Pd loading because of the significant absence of -NH_2 moieties. TGA curves (Figure S2) give a frank account on this extent as materials obtained after 5 min reaction time showed a double jump in the region $300\text{-}500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ corresponding to both the linker and MOF decomposition. The optimal candidate selected for further analysis and Pd loading was that indicated in entry 10, Table S1.

With these aspects in mind, we extended this optimized protocol to a larger scale inside a multimodal microwave reactor. We were able to obtain up to 317 mg material in a monomodal microwave (20 min microwave-assisted synthesis vs. 24 h in solvothermal method), while using a multimodal microwave the synthesis was scaled-up, producing *ca.* 1 g material in only 20 min. Although *a priori* yields were lower using the multimodal reactor (91 vs. 84% in mono and multimodal microwave instruments, respectively, $n=5$), space-time yield (STY) values were higher in the large-scale procedure ($1450\text{ Kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$) because of the higher concentration of the chemical species compared to the former scenario ($760\text{ Kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$). Notably, physicochemical properties did not significantly differ between materials obtained using mono- and multimodal instruments, as deduced from the following section. Note that, despite those materials obtained after 5 min were discarded for catalytic purposes (because its poor crystallinity), we confirmed the positive match with UiO-66 structure (Figure S1a) providing STYs $> 3100\text{ Kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$. This value is of extreme relevance for industrial fabrication as the highest value reported to date for this MOF in a continuous process was

2250 Kg·m⁻³·day⁻¹, indicating the suitability of this process for industrial scale-up.⁵⁸ Finally, for catalytic purposes, UiO-66-NH₂ nanocrystals were decorated with the active Pd species using a simple and efficient microwave-assisted reducing procedure (150 °C for 10 min), resulting in composites denoted as Pd(4.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ and Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂, containing 4.7 and 1.7 wt% Pd, respectively (based on ICP analysis).

3.2. Characterization of UiO-66-NH₂ and Pd@UiO-66-NH₂

PXRD patterns of pristine UiO-66-NH₂, Pd(4.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ and Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ (Figure S5) were compared to that corresponding to the simulated UiO-66 pattern (CCDC-1405751). Despite the success in the synthesis of this MOF, the peak broadening effect observed after Pd(II) loading and its further reduction to Pd NPs indicated a slight matrix degradation. It is worth to mention that MOF matrices can be partially damaged when *in-situ* preparing metal NPs under harsh reduction conditions (*i.e.* NaBH₄). The absence of the characteristic diffraction peaks of Pd, *e.g.* the most intense at *ca.* 40° corresponding to (111) plane, suggested the generation of non-aggregated Pd colloids with particle size smaller than the diffraction limit.⁵⁹ The FTIR spectra of UiO-66-NH₂ and Pd@UiO-66-NH₂ composites were similar to those reported in the literature (Figure S6),⁶⁰ including the most relevant bands: those of amino groups (NH₂, 3500-3390 cm⁻¹), carboxylic groups (COO, 1573 and 1385 cm⁻¹), and aromatic rings (C=C, 1499 cm⁻¹). Note that after the Pd incorporation, the IR bands were not significantly modified, probably due to the low Pd content. The thermal stability of the MOF and Pd-composites was roughly estimated by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) an inert (Ar) atmosphere. In the TGA of UiO-66-NH₂ (see Figure S7), three steps were observed: the first one corresponds to the water evaporation (100°C), the second one is related to the weight loss due to the hydroxylation of the -OH groups (*ca.* 300-350°C), and the last one (350°C) is associated to the MOF decomposition and oxidation to ZrO₂. Upon the Pd NPs incorporation, the thermal stability of the Pd@UiO-66-NH₂ composites decreases until 300°C, which may be due to the generation of extended defects caused by microwave irradiation (see Figure S7), as described elsewhere.²⁷ However, note here that the accurate estimation of the defects amount was not possible due to the lower material stability (*i.e.* defect concentration estimated as in ref. 31 upon normalization of TGA curves at 600 °C, using 350°C as the starting point of defect removal).

Further, in order to provide some insight on the dimension, distribution and location of Pd NPs, gas sorption and HAADF-STEM characterization were performed on the UiO-66-NH₂ and Pd@UiO-66-NH₂ composites. The UiO-66-NH₂ material showed the traditional type-I sorption isotherm (Figure S8), with BET surface area (S_{BET}) and micropore volume (V_p) of 1035 m²·g⁻¹ and 0.34 cm³·g⁻¹, respectively, in agreement with reported values.⁵³ After the Pd deposition, those values slightly

decreased for Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ ($S_{\text{BET}} = 1001 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$ and $V_p = 0.32 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$) and more noticeably in the case of Pd(4.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ ($S_{\text{BET}} = 757 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$ and $V_p = 0.23 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$), supporting the presence of Pd NPs within the MOF matrix.

In an attempt to precisely locate the Pd NPs, HAADF-STEM was performed for UiO-66-NH₂ and Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂. The morphology of UiO-66-NH₂ particles was preserved and remained unaltered after Pd(II) reduction under microwave radiation, as deduced from HAADF-STEM observations (Figure 2). The Pd NPs, with an estimated particle size of 3-4 nm (see Fig. 2e), seems to be homogeneously distributed within the MOF matrix (Figure 2c,d, see Videos 1).

Figure 2. HAADF-STEM images of UiO-66-NH₂ (a, b) and Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ (c, d); magnification x50000 and x150000, respectively; e) particle size distribution of Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂.

3.3. Hydrogenation of olefins

The catalytic activity of the Pd@UiO-66-NH₂ composites was evaluated for the selective hydrogenation of olefins to the corresponding alkanes under mild conditions (1 bar H₂, 25 °C). The reduction of 1-hexene was selected as model reaction, comparing the catalytic activity of the composites (Pd@UiO-66-NH₂) with several references: the commercial catalyst Pd/Al₂O₃, commonly used in this reaction,⁶¹ the pristine UiO-66-NH₂ and PVP-stabilized Pd NPs (PVP-Pd NPs). Hexane (compound 2a) and 2-hexene (compound 3a) can be obtained as reduction and side isomerization

products, respectively. Table 1 shows the results in terms of conversion of 1-hexene, its corresponding TOF, as well as selectivity, yield to the targeted product (n-hexane) for the catalysts prepared and tested under different conditions.

Table 1 Catalytic performance of the different samples in terms of conversion, selectivity, yield and turnover frequency (TOF) values.

Entry	Catalyst ^a	mol %	Time (h)	Conversion (%) ^d	Selectivity (%) ^d (2a/3a)	Yield (%) ^d (2a)	TOF ^e (h ⁻¹)
1	No catalyst	-	3	0	-/-	0	0
2	UiO-66-NH ₂	-	3	0	-/-	0	0
3	Pd(4.7%)@UiO-66-NH ₂	0.09	3	100	100/-	>99	377
4	Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH ₂	0.03	3	100	100/-	>99	1043
5	Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH ₂	0.03	2	100	100/-	>99	1565
6	Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂	0.03	1	100	100/-	>99	3130
7	Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH ₂	0.03	0.5	72	63/47	56	-
8	Pd(5%)/Al ₂ O ₃ ^b	0.03	1	100	82/18	70	2191
9	Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH ₂ ^c	0.03	6	100	100/-	94	7846
10	PVP-Pd NPs	0.05	1	6	42/58	3	-
11	PVP-Pd NPs	0.10	1	100	46/54	45	393

Reaction conditions: 10 mg of catalyst, 25 mL of a solution of 1-hexene (5 mmol) in ethyl acetate, 1 bar H₂, 25 °C, unless stated otherwise.

^a wt% of Pd calculated by ICP-OES

^b Reaction conditions: 3.4 mg of catalyst, 25 mL of a solution of 1-hexene (5 mmol) in ethyl acetate.

^c Reaction under solvent free conditions: 10 mg of catalyst, 10 mL of 1-hexene (80 mmol), 8 bar H₂, 25 °C for 6 h.

^d Conversion, selectivity and yield were determined by GC using cyclohexanol as internal standard and the corresponding products were identified by GC-MS.

^e TOF calculated as mol of product (hexane) *per* mol of metal *per* hour

Reference reactions (entries 1 and 2), either in absence or presence of the parent MOF, resulted in not-measurable conversion, confirming that the Pd species are the main responsible of the catalytic activity. Subsequently, the catalytic performance of the Pd(4.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ composite, with a similar Pd content than that found in the commercial catalyst (5%), was evaluated. After 3 h, a total conversion with excellent selectivity towards hexane was achieved (entry 3). Interestingly, when the Pd loading of the composite decreased from 4.7 to 1.7%, similar catalytic results were reached (100% conversion and 100% selectivity to hexane), highlighting the outstanding catalytic activity of the defective Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ (entry 4), with remarkably higher TOF values than those obtained with a higher Pd loading.

Reaction time was then shortened to optimize the catalytic conditions, observing full conversion and 100% selectivity towards hexane after 2 and 1 h (entries 5 and 6), achieving an excellent TOF value (3130 h⁻¹, entry 6). Nevertheless, these values significantly decreased (72% conversion and 63% selectivity) when the reaction proceeded for only 0.5 h (entry 7). Thus, 1 h was selected as the optimal reaction time. The competition between isomerization and reduction has been reported before for this reaction.⁶² Previous studies using MOF-based composites did not usually observe this effect because of the used extreme reaction conditions (high H₂ pressure and/or long reaction times, which favor the olefin hydrogenation) unlike the milder conditions in this work (1 bar H₂).

Pd leaching was discarded under such conditions, aspect that was confirmed when removing Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ from the media after 15 min reaction time (51% conversion). Then, the resulting supernatant was stirred for extra 45 min in the absence of the catalyst. Under such conditions, conversion of 1-hexene did not increase (Figure S9), suggesting the existence of a strong interaction between the Pd NPs and the MOF avoiding their release to the media, as conversion would have increased otherwise. In addition, the oxidation states of the constituent elements of the UiO-66-NH₂ and Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ catalysts were analyzed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). XPS spectra survey (Figure 3a) show the presence of Zr, C, O and N atoms in both samples, which are the main components of the MOF. The 3d Pd signal is only observed in Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂,

which can be deconvoluted to four peaks (Fig. 3b). The strong Pd 3d_{5/2} and Pd 3d_{3/2} peaks at 337 and 342 eV are attributed to Pd⁰, confirming the formation of Pd NPs. Nevertheless, the two less intense peaks at 338 and 343 eV can be assigned to Pd²⁺,⁶³ suggesting that a small fraction of Pd remains oxidized in the composite. This can be due to the re-oxidation of the dispersed Pd NPs in presence of air, which agrees with previous works.⁶⁴ In both spectra, the Zr 3p doublet is observed at *ca.* 334 and 348 eV (Figure 3b), while the Zr 3d signal can be deconvoluted into two peaks (184 and 186 eV), assigned to Zr⁴⁺ (Figure 3c). Finally, the N 1s peak for Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ is slightly shifted to higher binding energy values (402 eV) and broadened as compared to the spectrum of UiO-66-NH₂ (400 eV) (Figure 3d), suggesting the formation of interactions between the amine groups of the ligand of the MOF and the Pd species.³⁵

Figure 3. XPS spectra of UiO66-NH₂ and Pd(1.7%)/UiO-66-NH₂ a) survey, b) Zr 3p and Pd 3d regions, c) Zr 3d region and d) N1s region.

Upon the catalytic reaction, Pd(1.7%)/UiO-66-NH₂ was analyzed by PXRD and XPS. The crystalline structure of the MOF-based composite was kept (see Figure S10) and the Pd 3d XPS spectrum (Figure S11) showed only the peaks corresponding to Pd⁰ (337 and 342 eV), which suggests

that the re-oxidized Pd²⁺ species, present in the fresh composite catalyst, do not exist after the catalytic hydrogenation (1 h reaction time). Note that the re-oxidized Pd²⁺ species could persist after 30 min of reaction time, regardless of the presence of H₂ gas. This could explain the lower selectivity (63% selectivity, entry 7), since Pd(II) catalyzes isomerization *vs.* hydrogenation.⁶⁵ In addition, ICP analyses confirmed that the Pd content before and after the catalysis remains the same (1.69±0.08 *vs.* 1.56±0.08%), supporting the absence of Pd leaching during the reaction.

The performance of the composite was compared against a commercially available catalyst, Pd(5%)@Al₂O₃. In this case, full conversion was also achieved, but the selectivity towards the alkane was lower (82% selectivity, entry 8), which could be ascribed to the presence of Pd(II) species.⁶⁶ Besides, Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ exhibited a better hydrogenation activity than that achieved by the commercial catalyst (TOF = 3130 *vs.* 2191 h⁻¹), suggesting a potential catalytic enhancement of Pd NPs when incorporated within the MOF matrix and despite the higher Pd loading in the latter material. Comparing the catalytic results of our composite with other reported studies (Table S2), the catalytic hydrogenation activity of Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ was significantly superior than that observed with other UiO-66-based composites (*e.g.* the hierarchically porous Pt@UiO-66-NH₂-2h:⁶⁷ TOF = 1007 h⁻¹ or Pt@UiO-66:⁶⁸ TOF = 500 h⁻¹), and other well-known MOF composites (Pt/MIL-88b (Cr):⁶⁹ TOF = 1052 h⁻¹ or Pt/NiBDC (Ni):⁶⁹ TOF = 989 h⁻¹).

In order to shed some light on the effect of the MOF as Pd NPs host, the hydrogenation of 1-hexene was carried out in the presence of PVP-Pd NPs, which exhibit similar average size compared to Pd NPs in the UiO-66-NH₂ (average size of 4 nm, see Fig. S12). The tested catalytic content was higher than that in the composite (entries 10 and 11, 0.05 and 0.10 *vs.* 0.03 mol%). Lower conversion (6%, entry 10) was obtained when using 0.05 mol%, supporting the role of the MOF as a synergetic catalytic platform for well-accessible and dispersed Pd NPs. Only after using 0.10 mol% PVP-Pd NPs (entry 11), complete conversion was reached, but a quite lower selectivity was found in both cases (42-46% of selectivity towards alkane), stressing the relevance of the support in this process. In addition, the reaction was also performed over the Pd(1.7%)@UiO66-NH₂ composite under solvent free conditions. This provides a safer and more environmentally friendly process to efficiently produce alkanes from alkenes. Remarkably, Pd(1.7%)@UiO66-NH₂ successfully catalyzed the solvent-free hydrogenation of 1-hexene (10 mL, 0.08 moles) into the corresponding hexane, after 6 h and only consuming 8 bar of H₂, demonstrating its high catalytic hydrogenation performance in a solvent-free mode (TOF = 7846 h⁻¹).

A screening of different olefins as substrates was performed under the optimized conditions, the results being presented in Table 2. In the case of linear alkenes (1-octene and 1-tridecene, entries 1 and 2, respectively), the length of the alkyl chain had a negligible impact on the catalytic performance (full

conversion, >95% yield). Similar results were observed in the hydrogenation of cyclohexene (entry 3) and anethole (entry 4). The generation of by-products was negligible in the reactions mentioned above, demonstrating that Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ shows a superior selectivity towards the alkane formation. Finally, the hydrogenation of a bulky alkene, tetraphenyl ethylene, was also investigated (entry 5). The dimensions of this alkene (6.7 Å) may hinder its diffusion throughout the cavities of UiO-66-NH₂ (6.0 Å).³⁶ Thus, the composite showed a relatively low conversion (32%, entry 5), supporting the presence of some catalytically active species on the outer surface of the composite. However, the main active Pd species, also responsible for the selectivity, might be confined inside the MOF matrix, in agreement with the HAADF-STEM observations (Fig S13 a,b and c).

Table 2. Reaction scope

Entry ^a	Substrate	Product	Conversion ^c (%)	Yield ^c (%)
1	1b , R ₁ =butyl; R ₂ =R ₃ =R ₄ =H		100	95
2	1c , R ₁ =undecyl; R ₂ =R ₃ =R ₄ =H		100	99
3	1d , R=cyclohexyl		100	99
4	1e , R ₁ = <i>p</i> - anisole; R ₂ =R ₃ =H; R ₄ =- methyl		100	100

5

1f, R₁=
R₂=R₃=R₄=Ph

32

27

Reaction conditions: 10 mg of Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂, 25 mL of a solution of alkene (5 mmol) in ethyl acetate, 1 bar of H₂, 25 °C. Conversion and yield were determined by GC and the corresponding products were identified by GC-MS using cyclohexanol as internal standard.

To further probe the catalytic hydrogenation properties of the Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ platform under mild conditions (3 bar H₂, 25 °C, 1 h), a complex mixture of alkenes (including 1-hexene, 1-tridecene, and anethole) was tested (Scheme 1). The conversion and alkane selectivity for the three alkenes was 100%, showing no preference for any substrate.

Scheme 1. Hydrogenation of a complex mixture of alkenes using Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂

The recyclability of Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ catalyst was studied for the hydrogenation of 1-hexene without applying any regeneration treatment. The results indicated that the high activity of the composite was preserved after four cycles, observing a slight decrease in the selectivity in the 4th run 100 vs. 86%). This might be caused by a Pd NPs migration/aggregation (Fig 4c) and a decrease on the MOF crystallinity (Fig. S14).

Figure 4. a) Hydrogenation cycles of the Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ catalyst; TEM images of: b) fresh Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ catalyst and c) Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ catalyst after four cycles

Precisely locating Pd NPs within/onto MOFs is extremely challenging both from the synthetic and characterization point of views. However, several evidences throughout this work have supported that catalytically active species are equally distributed within and onto UiO-66-NH₂ crystals. For instance, the conversion of the bulkier tetraphenyl ethylene, not able to diffuse to CUS inside the MOF, is also in agreement with the partial location of Pd NPs onto the MOF external surface. To preferentially remove the Pd NPs located on the outer MOF crystal while preserving those inside the porosity/framework, the composite Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ was treated with a solution of K₂S₂O₈ (5 equiv.) in HCl (2 M) (Figure S15). This reagent was previously used for the oxidative redispersion of Pd(0) into Pd(II) cations in a different MOF, the MIL-101-NH₂.⁷⁰ Thus, this treatment successfully eliminated the external Pd NPs, keeping those inside the porosity/framework, as confirmed by HAADF-STEM images (Fig. S13d,e and f). Upon an oxidative treatment of only 15 min, the material continued demonstrating an important catalytic activity for olefin hydrogenation, but associated with a significant loss of selectivity (entry 2, Table 3). This aspect was exacerbated when the oxidative treatment lasts for 45 min (entry 3), showing not only a selectivity decrease (from 100 to 62%) but also a reduction in the yield (from 100 to 53%). Note here that ICP revealed not significant differences

on the Pd content, regardless the oxidation extent (entries 2 and 3). The loss of selectivity was then associated to the presence of Pd(II) species, as mentioned above. Overall, Pd NPs are then associated to the reduction reaction, while isomerization is produced by the Pd(II) species. Further, the origin of the selectivity seems to reside in those Pd NPs located within the MOF porosity/framework, as demonstrated by those reactions performed with PVP-Pd NPs (entries 10 and 11; Table 1). Pd species inside MOF porosity were eventually oxidized during consecutive catalytic runs, as observed in Figure 4, losing the overall selectivity as a consequence of their progressive oxidation into Pd(II).

Table 3 Hydrogenation of 1-hexene using Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ before and after oxidative treatment.

Entry	Catalyst	Metal loading (wt%)	Treatment	Yield (%)	Selectivity (2a/3a)
1	Pd@UiO-66-NH ₂	1.74±0.08	---	100	100/-
2	Pd@UiO-66-NH ₂ (ox-15)	1.63±0.08	K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ /HCl (15 min)	100	95/5
3	Pd@UiO-66-NH ₂ (ox-45)	1.60±0.08	K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ /HCl (45 min)	53	62/38

4. Conclusions

In this work, we have optimized the synthesis of defective UiO-66-NH₂ nanocrystals (91% yield metal basis; 760 Kg·m⁻³·day⁻¹) for improving their stability and catalytic performance. The optimal candidate, obtained in a monomodal microwave reactor, showed a compromise between defects (18.2%, as missing linkers), textural properties (937 m²·g⁻¹ BET surface area), thermal stability (350 °C decomposition temperature by TGA) and particle size (23.4 nm). The procedure was successfully scaled-up using a multimodal microwave reactor, highlighting the industrial relevance of this method (86% yield metal basis; 1450 Kg·m⁻³·day⁻¹). The resulting MOF was loaded with Pd(II) through wet impregnation followed by microwave radiation (150 °C, 10 min) to obtain small and homogeneously distributed Pd NPs (3-4 nm), as demonstrated by HAADF-STEM. The defective Pd(1.7%)@UiO-66-NH₂ composite was able to selectively hydrogenate challenging alkenes under milder reaction conditions (full conversion by using 1 bar H₂, room temperature) than those used in previous studies.

We identified the robust interaction and synergetic effects between both materials (Pd NPs and UiO-66-NH₂) in the composite as the origin of the selectivity (hydrogenation vs isomerization), achieving a superior activity compared to the commercially available Pd(5%)/Al₂O₃ catalyst (TOF = 3130 vs. 2191 h⁻¹, respectively), with recyclability for 3 consecutive runs.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9CY01234A>:

Additional experimental details (Table S1), figures (including PXRD patterns, TGA curves, Nitrogen sorption isotherms, FTIR spectra, Leaching test, XPS spectra, TEM image, HAADF-STEM images, ¹H NMR spectra of catalytic products), comparison of catalytic hydrogenation activity of MOF-based composites (Table S2) (PDF).

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